

Da'wah as a Strategy for Strengthening Entrepreneurial Character: Content Analysis and the Role of Religious Communication at the Bulukumba Vocational Training Center

By: **A. Muh Fadil Insana Jafar**¹, **Kamaluddin Tajibu**², **St. Nasriah**³

Pascasarjana UIN Alauddin Makassar

Email: andimhammadfadil188@gmail.com, kamaluddin.tajibu@uin-alauddin.ac.id, stnasriah@uin-alauddin.ac.id

Submission date: March 2025

Accepted date: March 2025

Published in: April 2025

Abstracts:

This research aims to describe the ethical role of da'wah messages in building labor independence at the Bulukumba Regency Job Training Center (BLK). With a qualitative and da'wah communication approach, this research collects data from primary and secondary sources through interviews, observation, and documentation. The results showed that the da'wah messages delivered, such as aqidah (sincerity), sharia (charity), muamalah (responsibility), and morals (honesty), were not only related to the provision of material but also formed the character and moral values of the trainees. This research implies the importance of integrating religious values in training programs to form a workforce that is technically skilled and has high moral integrity, highlighting the ethical responsibility of educators and practitioners in the field.

Keywords: Da'wah, messagesentreprenurship, BLK Bulukumba.

INTRODUCTION

One of the problems faced by developing countries, including Indonesia, is unemployment. A high unemployment rate can hamper regional development and cause other social problems. According to the Central Bureau of Statistics, the labor force is the total working and non-working population aged over 15 years. Unemployment occurs because fewer jobs are available than job seekers, and the competence of job seekers does not match the labor market (Nazara, 2008).

The Vocational Training Center (BLK) is a place of job training for the community to master specific work competencies. BLK Bulukumba Regency trained many alums who later became independent individuals and could work for themselves and their families. However, the awareness of the Bulukumba community about working is still low, so the role of da'wah is needed to change the community's mindset through religious messages.

Being unemployed is not favored in Islam. Islam encourages people to work independently to fulfill their needs and help others economically through charity, donation, and Zakat. Allah emphasizes in the Qur'an that humanity should not be idle; Allah commands humanity to work. Allah says in QS At-Taubah/9: 105.

وَقُلْ اَعْمَلُوا فَسَيَرَى اللّٰهُ عَمَلَكُمْ وَرَسُولُهُ وَالْمُؤْمِنُونَ وَسَتُرَدُّونَ اِلَىٰ عِلْمِ الْغَيْبِ وَالشَّهَادَةِ فَيُنَبِّئُكُمْ بِمَا كُنْتُمْ تَعْمَلُونَ

Translation:

"And say: 'Work, and Allah and His Messenger and the believers will see your work, and you will be returned to the One Who knows the unseen and the manifest, and He will tell you what you have done. (Kementerian Agama RI, 2009)

According to M. Quraish Shihab, the above verse aims to encourage humanity to be more introspective and supervise their deeds or work by reminding them that every good and bad deed or deed has a nature that cannot be hidden and has witnesses who know and see its essence, namely Allah, Prophet Muhammad PBUH, and witnesses from Muslims. After that, Allah will open the veil that covers the eyes of those who do these deeds or deeds on the Day of Judgment so that they also know and see the nature of their deeds. Meanwhile, according to Muhammad Amin Suma, human beings are commanded by Allah always to do work that is beneficial for themselves and others. Because all deeds will be seen by Allah, the Messenger, and the believers and shown by Allah on the Day of Judgment, they will be rewarded according to their deeds while on earth. If the deeds are good, they will be rewarded; if they are bad, they will be punished. (Kurniawan, 2019).

From the explanation of the opinion above, it can be said that this verse explains the prohibition of not working, especially for men who are married with the obligation to provide for their wives and children; besides that, Allah commands his servants to work with halal work without disturbing Islamic law. One of the jobs that can be done is entrepreneurship.

Entrepreneurship is creating added value by managing resources creatively and innovatively. Creativity is the ability to develop new ideas and ways of solving problems and finding opportunities. Meanwhile, innovation is the ability to apply creativity to solve problems and find opportunities. Creative thinking allows entrepreneurs to see things from a different perspective. Entrepreneurs can create various new and different things, such as processes, methods, goods, and services, that can add value and competitive advantages. (Sanawiri and Iqbal 2018).

Job Training Center, or BLK, is a place where the process of job training is organized for trainees so that they can master a certain type and level of work competence to equip themselves to enter the job market and independent businesses or as a training place to increase their work productivity so as to improve their welfare (Regulation of the Minister of Manpower and Transmigration of the Republic of Indonesia 2012: Article 1, Paragraph 1).

This vocational training center trains community workers who have dropped out of school to be trained in skills. The skills that will be trained are maintenance of light vehicle systems injection, audio video engineering, installation of industrial electrical automation installations, graphic design, making fashion decorations with manual border machines, 3G position smaw welding, and architectural draftsman. With this institution, it is hoped that it will create a skilled and qualified community so that the quality of the workforce increases and can compete. By following the work program at BLK, job seekers and unemployed people can improve their work skills according to the job market's needs, and trainees can also become entrepreneurs independently.

Job training centers in Indonesia have spread widely to various provinces, one of which is the province of South Sulawesi, specifically in Bulukumba Regency. BLK Bulukumba Regency is one of the BLKs that has been established for a long time and already has many alumni spread throughout Indonesia. In contrast to other BLKs, the programs offered at BLK Bulukumba Regency are limited to only four programs: garment fashion technology, electricity, automotive, and furniture. There have been many alums from BLK Bulukumba who, after attending training, have become independent individuals who can work for themselves and their families, one of which is the 2020 and 2021 alumni who will be the research sample.

Based on data on the labor force participation rate in Bulukumba Regency in 2021 of around 65.46%, male TPAK reached 81.83%, and female TPAK was 51.23%. Meanwhile, the data on the Employment Opportunity Rate (TKK) in 2021 reached 96.86%, with the TKK of the male population around 96.31% and the TKK of the female population around 97.62%. Data on the Open Unemployment Rate (TPT) in 2021 was recorded at 3.14%, with a TPT for the male population of around 3.69% and a TPT for the female population of around 2.38%. As for the highest level of education completed, the working population in Bulukumba is dominated by those who graduated from elementary school and below. The details are around 47.60% who work with elementary school diplomas and below, junior high school equivalent as much as 15.51%, high school equivalent as much as 22.56%, and high school graduates and above as much as 14.33%. (Badan Pusat Statistik Kabupaten Bulukumba 2021:11).

Based on the data above, it can be seen that the people of Bulukumba still lack the awareness to work, even though the government has provided various options and facilities to find work and job training. Given conditions like this, the role of da'wah, which provides religious messages, is needed to change the mindset of the people of Bulukumba Regency.

Da'wah messages encourage entrepreneurship development through entrepreneurship training, business capital assistance, market access, and mentoring for prospective entrepreneurs. In addition to economic aspects, da'wah messages can explore relevant religious values, such as social justice, concern for others, and sustainable management of natural resources. These messages can encourage the community to contribute to addressing unemployment issues through responsible entrepreneurial initiatives socially and environmentally.

Several previous studies have examined the role of religious teachings in workforce development. For example, research by Maulana (2019) shows that Islamic values such as honesty, responsibility, and sincerity can improve work ethic and productivity. However, there is still a gap in research on how da'wah messages can be effectively integrated into job training programs, especially in rural areas such as Bulukumba. This study aims to fill that gap by exploring the role of da'wah messages in building entrepreneurship at BLK Bulukumba Regency.

METHODS

This research uses a qualitative approach with a da'wah communication method. The research was conducted at the BLK Office of Bulukumba Regency. Primary data sources were obtained through interviews with six key informants, including two heads of BLK and four trainees. The selection of informants was based on their strategic role in delivering da'wah messages and their direct experience in training. Secondary data sources were obtained from literature, journals, and articles. Data were collected through observation, interviews, and documentation. Data analysis was conducted through three stages: data reduction, presentation, and conclusion drawing. Credibility testing was conducted through extended observation, triangulation, and peer discussion.

DISCUSSION

The presence of the Work Training Center (BLK) in Bulukumba Regency is a thanksgiving for the people of Bulukumba Regency because, with this BLK, the people of Bulukumba Regency have a place to develop *skills* or skills in the world of work. The Vocational Training Center (BLK) is not just a physical building but also a symbol of concern and commitment to building a strong foundation for the community. The Vocational Training Center was established to provide skills and knowledge to job seekers who hope for the community to increase employment opportunities.

After conducting research in the form of observations and interviews with several informants on what happened in the field, there are findings on the role of the head and instructors of the Bulukumba Regency BLK in delivering the da'wah message. As for some of the roles carried out by the head and instructor of BLK in delivering da'wah messages at activities at BLK Bulukumba Regency, namely:

1. Facilitator

The Head of the Vocational Training Center (BLK) in Bulukumba Regency is a central facilitator in delivering da'wah messages to the workforce in various activities organized at the BLK. As the prominent leader, the Head of BLK plays a strategic role in designing, directing, and implementing training programs that focus on developing technical skills and providing adequate facilities. As a facilitator, the Head of BLK is tasked with ensuring the delivery of technically practical training and establishing an inclusive learning atmosphere that supports the holistic growth of participants.

The Head of BLK must be able to adjust the approach according to the diversity of participants when delivering the proselytization message. Facilitation is about teaching and building emotional connections, listening, and responding to each individual's needs. It must be a guide who can guide participants through challenges, encourage self-reflection, and inspire a spirit of achievement through the practice and beliefs of each religion.

Currently, the head of BLK has carried out some of his roles as a facilitator. He provides several facilities to participants who take part in training at BLK Bulukumba, one of which is attending training free of charge.

2. Motivator

The Head and Instructors of the Vocational Training Center (BLK) in Bulukumba Regency are vital motivators in delivering da'wah messages to the workforce in various activities at BLK. As a leader, the Head of BLK is not only tasked with organizing training programs but must also be able to encourage enthusiasm and motivation for participants. The head and instructors also serve as role models in applying religious and moral values in their daily actions, creating an inspiring and supportive atmosphere for participants' spiritual and professional growth.

The motivation provided by BLK Heads and Instructors is not only limited to the individual level but also extends to the group level. By fostering positive relationships and motivating each other, the workforce can feel the power of community that supports the trainees' spiritual and professional growth.

The head and instructors of the Bulukumba Vocational Training Center have passionately delivered da'wah messages to motivate trainees. Dedicatedly inviting participants to see every challenge as an opportunity to grow and develop. The da'wah message focuses on technical skills and emphasizes the importance of forming a strong character and work ethic. Through encouraging words and motivational stories, they seek to motivate participants to have a positive mentality, resilience, and determination to achieve their dreams. These proselytizing messages create a vibrant training environment and guide participants toward a successful and meaningful career journey. Zainal, an instructor at BLK Bulukumba, said:

"So every time we train the participants, we give them an understanding and motivation on how to acquire the skills, especially to maintain the skills, meaning that the skills should not be lost after the training. (Zainal Abidin Interview, 8 December 2023)

Based on the results of the interview above, it can be said that every training held at BLK Bulukumba not only teaches technical skills but also motivates participants. The motivation aims to help them understand the importance of maintaining and developing the skills they have obtained during training.

Similarly, Susmiati, as the instructor of BLK Bulukumba, argued that:

"For the participants, before entering the training, they are equipped with what is called soft skills, so there is a separate teacher, usually the head of the KTU, who teaches about soft skills, how to motivate students about future work after attending training, so if for instructors, they usually motivate how to study well, how to make patterns well but if for general motivation, we usually take lecturers from outside. That is where everything is how the stages when you want to work, such as making applications and interview tests, are all taught, so usually after students participate, there is rarely unemployment after participating in training because the motivation is extraordinary for the teacher, so we bring in special teachers who provide closed motivation, the name is soft skills. (Susmiati, Interview, 7 December 2023)

Based on the interview results above, it can be seen that BLK Bulukumba strongly emphasizes the need to maintain and continue to care for the skills obtained so that they do not just disappear. Meanwhile, Susmiati added that trainees have been equipped with *soft skills* from the beginning, including motivation from outside teachers who are experts in encouraging. These skills include technical skills and important stages in finding and keeping a job. Thus, training at BLK Bulukumba provides practical skills and equips participants with a foundation soft enough to achieve success in the world of work skills.

The motivation often given by the head and instructors of BLK to all participants and alums is not to become unemployed but to be enthusiastic about working and becoming successful entrepreneurs.

As Yusuf as, the Head of BLK Bulukumba, said:

In this case, it is actually packaged in training; there are hours of lessons in which productivity is trained on how to do business mentally, and there are efforts if things happen that are not quite right, such as expectations without improving the performance is down there we train mentally including guidance to direct them to get financial business costs problems, such as being directed to related agencies that the licensing is like this, we are directed and even appealed to after attending the training so that they take care of the job seeker card or what is known as the yellow card. (Yusuf, Interview December 7, 2023).

Apart from the motivation to become entrepreneurs, instructors also often provide space motivation to participants or alums who want to work in the industrial world. Zainal, as a furniture instructor, said:

We do not limit it to just one target, so there are two targets for our training completion: it can enter the industry or entrepreneurship. Whatever allows entrepreneurs to produce financially where the entrepreneurs can survive, it does not matter whether they want to be in the industry or entrepreneurship; it does not matter. (Zainal Abidin, Interview, December 8, 2023)

Mr. Muh. Ashary, also an alumnus of BLK Bulukumba, added that:

Before we take part in program activities, there are stages that we must pass, for example, character building and mental formation; it could be because what I feel is that there are instructors who always direct us, and sometimes we are given mental pressures so that our mentality in building future businesses can be overcome when there are problems that we have to pass. (Muh. Ashary, Interview December 7, 2023)

Based on the interviews above, it can be said that the role of the head and instructors in training at BLK is not only as facilitators but also as motivators. Through productive lessons and mentoring, trainees are equipped with the skills to succeed in entrepreneurship and overcome challenges and crises that may arise in the business world. In addition, it gives trainees the flexibility to choose their career path after completing the training, be it by working in industry or starting their own business. This approach creates wider opportunities and empowers participants to succeed in the industry and as entrepreneurs.

The head and instructors at Bulukumba Vocational Training Center (BLK) are significant motivators for participants. The head of BLK, as a leader, provides direction, encouragement, and support to the whole team and creates an environment conducive to learning and skills development. By being motivators, BLK heads and instructors play a key role in helping participants overcome challenges, achieve, and form positive attitudes towards learning and working through habituation in religious experiences, especially the five daily prayers.

3. Tutor

Instructors at BLK have a central role in shaping and honing the skills of trainees, not just as information providers but also as mentors who are dedicated to guiding, inspiring, and supporting the development of each participant. With their expertise and experience, BLK instructors are able to deliver training materials in a clear and comprehensible manner, not only focusing on the technical aspects of skills but also paying attention to the attitudes and values that are important in the world of work. With an interactive and inclusive approach, instructors create a positive learning environment, allowing participants to grow and develop optimally through dedication and commitment.

Instructors play an active role in running the process of activities at BLK for 30 days per batch. Instructors advocate that every participant at Bulukumba Vocational Training Center (BLK) must actively engage in a variety of activities designed to improve their skills and knowledge. Each day, they are involved in theoretical learning sessions involving training materials that are tailored to the current needs of industry and the job market.

In addition, participants are also involved in hands-on activities to be able to apply theoretical knowledge to practical skills. These training activities involve the use of the latest equipment and technology in related industries, providing participants with hands-on experience that can enhance their readiness to enter the workforce and religious messages in spiritual guidance, such as reciting *basmalah* when starting work and saying *hamdalah* when finishing work.

Daily activities of BLK Bulukumba participants

Hours Activities

08.00-08.30 Attendance

08.30-11.30 Entry Material (Theory)

11.30-13.00 Rest

13.00-16.00 Practices

During these activities participants are given the opportunity to collaborate, communicate and network with fellow participants, creating an environment that supports growth and skills development. All of these activities are designed to ensure that BLK Bulukumba participants not only have solid theoretical knowledge but also practical skills that are relevant and applicable in a real work environment.

Overall, the message from the instructors and the head of BLK Bulukumba signaled that honesty is not just a plus but a key foundation that supports integrity, good communication, and building solid relationships, both in the world of training and entrepreneurship.

BLK Bulukumba alumni also said that they were always given an understanding of honesty in entrepreneurship or working in the industrial world by the head and instructors at BLK Bulukumba. One of them is as said by Diana, an alumnus of BLK Bulukumba; she said it must be honest too because if we face a client, it must not lie because trust is crucial. (Diana, Interview, December 13, 2023).

The same thing happened to Ahmad as an alumnus of BLK Bulukumba; he said:

Of course, there is honesty and consistency, and consistency is very much taught so that we continue to work according to existing procedures and not harm others. (Ahmad, Interview, December 7, 2023)

Likewise, Asmiani said:

If we are not honest, not on time, we usually run if we make a mistake, usually we make a mistake in cutting or ironing, we have to tell the person honestly and if it has to be replaced, it has to be replaced. (Asmiani, Interview December 13)

Based on the results of the interview above, it can be said that the alumni of BLK Bulukumba consistently stated that the value of honesty is a strong foundation in pursuing a career in the industrial or entrepreneurial world. They gained this understanding through guidance and direction from the head and instructors at BLK Bulukumba. Diana, one of the alumni, emphasized the importance of honesty in interacting with clients, considering that trust plays a crucial role in business relationships. Ahmad made a similar point, highlighting the importance of consistency and carrying out procedures honestly to prevent harm to other parties. Thus, BLK Bulukumba alums realize that integrity and honesty are essential values that must be upheld when pursuing a career in the industrial world.

4. Initiator

BLK heads and instructors have a significant role as initiators in creating and leading various learning programs and initiatives. The head of BLK, as the primary leader, is responsible for designing and launching training programs that are relevant to the needs of the job market. They act as initiators in formulating strategies for collaborative partnerships with industry and identifying the latest trends and developments in the world of work.

Yusuf stated that the Vocational Training Center (BLK) is only limited to teaching skills and does not provide support in finding a job. However, it needs to be recognized that the head of the BLK also has initiatives and collaborations that are oriented toward channeling graduates into the world of work. Yusuf underlined that there are industrial companies that collaborate with BLK to find prospective workers who are skilled and in accordance with the company's criteria. As the head of BLK, we welcome and actively accept such cooperation, recognizing the importance of bridging the gap between BLK graduates who have skills and industries that need qualified workers. (Yusuf, Interview December 7, 2023)

By facilitating this collaboration, BLK is not only responsible for teaching technical skills, but also helping BLK participants to connect directly with job opportunities that match their expertise. This is a proactive step in supporting BLK participants to enter the workforce more smoothly, increasing their chances of finding a job that matches the skills they have acquired during their training at BLK.

In addition, this collaboration also creates a good relationship between BLK and industry, strengthens BLK's position as a training institution that is responsive to labor market needs and expands career opportunities for participants. Thus, BLK is committed to not only provide skills, but also play an active role in helping participants achieve success in the world of work.

Meanwhile, the instructor acts as an initiator in developing an effective curriculum, developing relevant learning materials, and designing practical activities that enrich participants' experiences.

Zainal said that curriculum development should reflect industry needs and provide a solid foundation for participants' growth and development. By designing learning tools that are easy to understand and remember, instructors can improve the efficiency of participants' understanding of concepts and application of practical skills. This initiative includes the selection of appropriate learning methods, the use of industry-relevant teaching materials, and the integration of technology into the learning process. Zainal believes that by designing a curriculum that is responsive to industry developments and interactive learning tools, participants will be more motivated to develop their skills more effectively. (Zainal Abidin, Interview, December 8, 2023)

By taking on the role of initiator, BLK heads and instructors help shape the direction and focus of learning, ensuring that the programs organized at BLK match the needs of participants and the industry. In addition, they also serve as pioneers in introducing new technologies and innovations in the learning process, ensuring that participants are trained with modern and up-to-date methods. Thus, the role of an initiator not only creates a dynamic learning environment but also ensures that BLK continues to be a relevant training center that is responsive to changes in the world of work.

5. Organizer

The role of the head and instructors at the Vocational Training Center (BLK) as organizers plays a central role in determining the success and effectiveness of training program implementation. The head of BLK is responsible for planning, organizing and supervising all aspects of BLK operations.

Yusuf said that at the Bulukumba Vocational Training Center (BLK) there is a big responsibility held by the officers at the BLK as organizers. My job is to ensure that the programs at BLK run smoothly. This reflects an awareness of the key role played by BLK leaders in planning, organizing, and coordinating every aspect of the training program. (Yusuf, Interview December 7, 2023)

As an organizer, he is responsible for ensuring that every training session and activity at BLK takes place efficiently and effectively in accordance with the set objectives and standards. With a deep understanding of this task, Yusuf shows the seriousness and commitment of BLK Bulukumba in organizing quality training programs and providing a positive impact for participants.

On the other hand, BLK instructors act as organizers in designing and structuring learning materials, developing training schedules, and ensuring efficient use of resources. Instructors are also responsible for managing time, developing evaluations, and providing constructive feedback to optimize participants' learning.

Overall, the role of an organizer creates a structured and coordinated framework at BLK. This involves careful planning, efficient scheduling, and good organization to ensure that each training program runs smoothly and delivers optimal results. With the leadership and organizational skills of the BLK head and instructors, the institution can meet its goal of producing a competent workforce that is ready to compete in the industrial world.

The da'wah messages conveyed by the head and instructors of BLK are:

6. Akidah (sincerity)

The da'wah message in the form of sincerity teaches that sincerity in every action is the main foundation for strengthening beliefs and relationships with the Creator. The BLK head and instructors inspire participants to make sincerity the main foundation in every effort made, both in the world of training and in everyday life. This da'wah message encourages participants to reflect, introspect, and develop sincerity as the primary foundation for pursuing success. With the presence of the Head and Instructors who are full of sincerity, the Job Training Center is not only a place to learn skills but also a means to understand the true meaning of sincerity in various aspects of life.

According to Susmiati an instructor at BLK Bulukumba, said "Alhamdulillah, if it's like me because I am also active in religion, what I usually suggest is how we are sincere in working". (Susmiati, Interview December 7, 2023).

Agreeing with Nirwan as the BLK Bulukumba instructor, he said:

If the workshop is said to be a dime seeker, so we are dime seekers, it is natural that we do not care about the heat of the sun, someone in the middle of the road is damaged by his motorbike, coincidentally he cannot transport it there, well we have to be sincere in visiting the vehicle, that is what I teach students is sincere, because if you work it is not sincere, it means nothing, sometimes the car is also quickly damaged if it is in the workshop" (Nirwan, Interview, December 14, 2023).. (Nirwan, Interview December 14, 2023).

Based on the interviews above, it can be concluded that it is clear how important sincerity is in carrying out work, especially in the context of workshop training. Susmiati points out that sincerity in work is a highly recommended value, especially with her involvement in religious activities. She encourages sincerity as the foundation of every daily action.

On the handother , he is also of the opinion that emphasizing that even though the work in the workshop may be done under various difficult conditions, sincerity remains a key factor. Nirwan shared his practical experience of how sincerity in helping owners of vehicles that had broken down on the road became the essence of their job. He taught the value of sincerity to the students, emphasizing that without sincerity, the work in the workshop loses meaning, and even repaired vehicles can quickly deteriorate again.

Ahmad, an alumnus of BLK Bulukumba, expressed his views on the important role of the instructors of the Vocational Training Center (BLK) in teaching human values, especially about sincerity in helping others. According to him, BLK instructors have an excellent opportunity to shape the character of their students not only in technical skills but also in the aspect of social care. Ahmad emphasized that a sincere attitude in helping others is not just an action but also a form of deep concern for the sustainability of the common welfare. (Ahmad, Interview, December 7, 2023).

7. Sharia (charity)

The Sharia da'wah message about alms teaches that giving is a meaningful commandment in Islam. Almsgiving is not only about giving material or wealth but also about giving some of what you have to others as a form of love and care.

This da'wah message of almsgiving is not only related to giving material things but also involves various forms of kindness, such as providing moral assistance, knowledge, or positive experiences to others. This message reflects the importance of solidarity and care in establishing social relationships, as well as being a call to make alms part of a life routine that can form a noble and loving personality. Thus, this da'wah of alms not only teaches about giving but also invites participants to feel the joy of giving, which can be a path to a more meaningful life.

Susmiati, an instructor at BLK Bulukumba, said:

When we are well-established or have an income, how do we set aside time for charity to increase the amount of charity for people in need? (Susmiati, Interview, December 7, 2023).

Based on the interviews above, it can be concluded that after achieving financial success, we should consider setting aside some of our sustenance for charity. This conclusion views charity as a moral obligation and a noble act that can enrich the meaning of life. Thus, Susmiati suggests that one's success should not only be measured by material aspects but also by the ability to share with others. This conclusion creates an awareness of social responsibility after achieving success so that success can have a more significant positive impact on society and the environment.

Similarly, Muh. Ashary stated that BLK instructors often use this opportunity to remind students about the importance of charity as part of broader life principles. According to him, these da'wah messages not only affect individuals personally but also have the potential to form a society that is more caring and empathetic towards others. (Muh Ashary, Interview December 7, 2023)

Thus, Ashary views that BLK has a strategic role in spreading the values of goodness and da'wah to the younger generation, thus creating a sustainable positive impact in the social and spiritual development of society.

8. *Mu'amalah* (Responsibility)

The muamalah da'wah message about responsibility highlights the importance of awareness and commitment in carrying out our obligations towards Allah SWT, fellow humans, and the environment. Responsibility is not just a task that must be carried out but a mandate that must be carried out with full awareness and integrity. In the context of muamalah, responsibility includes various aspects such as trust in transactions, fulfillment of financial obligations, and wise management of resources.

The Head of BLK and the instructors passionately conveyed that every individual who participates in the training has a moral responsibility to the community and the surrounding environment. They emphasize that the skills acquired are not solely for personal gain but rather to make a positive contribution to the communities and industries where participants will later work. This proselytizing message creates awareness of the importance of bringing ethical values and responsibility to every step taken in the world of work so that trainees at BLK become not only skilled professionals but also responsible individuals who care about the social impact of their actions.

The preaching about keeping promises that are often delivered by the head and instructors of the Vocational Training Center has deep meaning as a foundation for successful and sustainable learning. Trainees are invited to reflect that promises are not just verbal commitments but moral principles that reflect the quality of character. Adherence to a promise not only shows obedience to rules but also measures personal integrity. In the context of training, keeping promises is key to creating a learning environment of mutual respect and appreciation. Therefore, this da'wah message invites every trainee to build a culture of mutual trust so that the learning process can run effectively, provide maximum benefits, and create individuals who are resilient and reliable in the world of work.

Yusuf, as the head of BLK Bulukumba, argued that:

"So the problems of da'wah messages to BLK alumni I often convey are consistent, actually keeping promises in providing services, for example in sewing, it often happens that it is boring, we as consumers in receiving services at the sewing agent if we promise a new one is not kept, because he often promises he cannot finish within the promised time, finally what is there we are not trusted to avoid like that, that's what I said." (Yusuf, Interview December 7, 2023).

Susmiati, the BLK Bulukumba instructor, also added her opinion. She said:

"So I always tell them that when you have received an order, treat the customer as well as possible so that no customer is hurt or disappointed, take care of his heart when one customer is disappointed, don't expect that his mouth can be held back, he will definitely tell here and there that ohh the tailor there is so bad like this, like this, try to treat the customer as well as possible, like how to serve and one thing never promise if it cannot be kept. Because why? We have to return to a tailor three or four times to have our clothes made, and then, if the work is not finished up to four times, we feel annoyed, and it is unlikely that we will go there again to have our clothes sewn. Alumni here, Alhamdulillah, for their promises, they already know that they cannot promise." (Susmiati, Interview December 7)

Based on the results of the above research, it can be concluded that consistency in keeping promises, especially regarding services to BLK participants, has a significant impact on trust and reputation. Yusuf highlighted the importance of keeping promises in providing services, especially in the sewing field, so that customers do not feel disappointed and lose trust. Meanwhile, Susmiati emphasized the need to treat customers well and advised against making promises that cannot be fulfilled, as this can create discomfort and disappointment on the part of customers. This conclusion illustrates how important integrity and responsibility are in maintaining customer trust and building a positive reputation.

Some participants also always remember the da'wah messages that are often conveyed by the head and instructors of BLK Bulukumba, as said by Ayu, an alumnus of BLK Bulukumba, she said "You can't make promises if you really can't finish, don't promise to say two days and three days are finished when they are not." (Ayu, Interview December 3, 2023).

Based on the results of the interview above, it can be concluded that the message that emerges is very clear, namely, not to make promises that cannot be kept. Promising completion within two or three days, but in reality, not being able to fulfill the promise can create distrust and disappointment on the part of the recipient. This message emphasizes the importance of integrity and honesty in communication and suggests only making promises that you are absolutely sure you can fulfill.

9. Akhlak (honesty)

Moral da'wah messages about honesty emphasize the importance of integrity and honesty in every aspect of life. Honesty is not just a behavior but a reflection of sincerity and loyalty to moral values. The head and instructors convey the da'wah message of honesty as the primary foundation in developing the skills and character of trainees. The head of the Vocational Training Center, with his exemplary leadership, emphasized that honesty is a non-negotiable principle. He detailed how honesty forms the basis of integrity and responsibility, which are crucial in the world of work.

As conveyed by Nirwan, he said:

The most important thing is K3, cleanliness, *secondly your health, then your nature and behavior outside, namely honesty. If you don't have that, the community's trust in you is automatic, because we as mechanics must be honest, disciplined, dexterous, and proficient.* (Nirwan, Interview December 14, 2023).

Zainal, as the BLK Bulukumba instructor, also said that:

How does he maintain integrity later outside when they have finished the integrity in which there is honesty? How to build communication with customers when entrepreneurship means that if he is already an entrepreneur, especially those who are entrepreneurial, how the price when someone orders is not too inflated in price compared to others, so the price is reasonable so the profit obtained is well not very profitable. (Zainal, Interview December 8, 2023)

This is in line with Yusuf as the head of BLK Bulukumba, he said "I often say that it is actually not expertise that makes us feel at home in relationships, but honesty, then we are consistent". (Yusuf, Interview December 7, 2023)

Based on the results of the interview above, it can be concluded that honesty plays a central role in maintaining public trust. As a mechanic, integrity and honesty are the basis of the trust given by customers. Zainal, an instructor at BLK Bulukumba, highlighted the importance of maintaining integrity outside of training, particularly in entrepreneurship. For entrepreneurs, honesty is not only reflected in reasonable prices but also in building good communication with customers.

The Head of BLK Bulukumba, added another dimension that honesty and consistency are more powerful keys than technical expertise in building good relationships. In other words, it is not only technical skills that make someone valued, but also integrity and honesty that are consistently maintained.

Overall, the message from the instructors and the head of BLK Bulukumba emphasized that honesty is not just a plus but is the main foundation that supports integrity, good communication, and building solid relationships, both in the world of training and entrepreneurship.

BLK Bulukumba alumni also said that they were always given an understanding of honesty in entrepreneurship or working in the industrial world by the head and instructors at BLK Bulukumba. One of them is Diana, an alumna of BLK Bulukumba. She said:

"We have to be honest too because when we are dealing with clients, we cannot lie because trust is essential" (Diana, Interview December 13, 2023)

The same thing with Ahmad as an alumna of BLK Bulukumba; he said:

"Of course, there is honesty about consistency, and consistency is very much taught so that we keep working according to existing procedures and do not harm others" (Ahmad, Interview, December 7, 2023).

Likewise, Asmiani said:

"If we are not honest, not on time, usually we also run if we make a mistake, we can make a mistake in cutting or ironing, we must tell the person honestly, and if it has to be replaced, it must be replaced." (Asmiani, Interview December 13, 2023)

Based on the results of the interview above, it can be concluded that the alumni of BLK Bulukumba consistently stated that the value of honesty is a strong foundation in pursuing a career in the industrial or entrepreneurial world. They gained this understanding through guidance and direction from the head and instructors at BLK Bulukumba. Diana, one of the alumni, emphasized the importance of honesty in interacting with clients, considering that trust plays a crucial role in business relationships. Ahmad made a similar point, highlighting the importance of consistency and carrying out procedures honestly to prevent harm to other parties. Thus, BLK Bulukumba alumni realize that integrity and honesty are essential values that must be upheld when pursuing a career in the industrial world.

This research is in line with the findings of Maulana (2019), which show that the integration of religious values into entrepreneurship education can improve work ethic and productivity. However, this study makes a new contribution by exploring how da'wah messages can be integrated into vocational training programs in rural areas. Compared to similar programs in other countries, such as Malaysia and Turkey, BLK Bulukumba is unique in its holistic da'wah approach, which not only focuses on technical skills but also on character building.

CONCLUSION

Based on the description of the previous chapter related to the discussion of research findings on da'wah messages in building entrepreneurship and independence of the workforce at BLK Bulukumba Regency, it can be concluded that the role of the head and instructors of BLK in delivering da'wah messages to the workforce activities at BLK Bulukumba

Regency is: as a facilitator, motivator, tutor, initiator, and organizer. The da'wah message is *aqidah* (sincerity), *sharia* (alms), *muamalah* (responsibility), and morals (honesty).

LITERATURE

- Ahmad. 2023. Interview. Alumni of BLK Bulukumba Regency, Office of BLK Bulukumba Regency, December 07.
- Asmiani. 2023. Interview. Alumni of BLK Bulukumba Regency, Mannaungi Village, December 13.
- Ayu, 2023. Interview. Bulukumba Regency BLK Trainee Alumni, Mannaungi Village, December 13.
- Badan Pusat Statistik (BPS) Bulukumba Regency. 2021. Employment Statistics of Bulukumba Regency.
- Diana. 2023. Interview. Bulukumba Regency BLK Trainee Alumni, Mannaungi Village, December 13.
- Jaharuddin, and Radiana Dhewayani. 2020. *Nazir & Entrepreneurship*. Cet. I. Yogyakarta: Hikam Library.
- Ministry of Religious Affairs RI. 2014. *Al-Qur'an and Translations*. Bandung: Haekal Media Center.
- Kurniawan, Rahmat. 2019. "The Urgency of Work in the Qur'an." *Journal Islamic Studies* 3(1).
- Maulana, Fikri. 2019. "Entrepreneurship Education in Islam." *Journal of Islamic Education* 2(1).
- Muh. Ashary. 2023. Interview. Alumni of BLK Participants of Bulukumba Regency, Alfamart Bulukumba City, December 07.
- Maulana, Fikri. 2019. "Entrepreneurship Education in Islam." *Journal of Islamic Education* 2(1).
- Nazara, Suahasil. 2008. "Manufacturing Industry Sector and Regional Development." Vol. II No. 3.
- Nirwan. 2023. Interview. Automotive Instructor of BLK Bulukumba Regency, Office of BLK Bulukumba Regency, December 14.
- Regulation of the Minister of Labor and Transmigration of the Republic of Indonesia. 2012. Number 7 of 2012 concerning General Provisions Article 1, Paragraph 1.
- Putong, Iskandar. 2008. *Economics: Introduction to Micro and Macro*. Jakarta: Mitra Wacana Media.
- Sanawiri, Brillyanes, and Mohammad Iqbal. 2018. *Entrepreneurship*. Cet. I. Malang: UB Press.
- Sinaga, Mangaradot Saur A. 2017. "Analysis of Factors Affecting the Unemployment Rate in North Sumatra." Thesis, Medan: Postgraduate Program, State University of Medan.
- Susmiati. 2023. Interview. Sewing Instructor of BLK Bulukumba Regency, Office of BLK Bulukumba Regency, December 07.
- Yusuf. 2023. Interview. Head of BLK Bulukumba Regency, Office of BLK Bulukumba Regency, December 07.
- Zainal Abidin. 2023. Interview. Furniture Instructor of BLK Bulukumba Regency, Office of BLK Bulukumba Regency, December 08.